

SEWING THREADS AND THEIR TYPES

Muratbaeva Kamila Ikramovna.

*2nd year student of Faculty of Industrial Technology
Karakalpak State University*

Abstract: *There are many types of yarns with different properties. These are pure spun yarns made directly or from various types of staple fibers, mixed yarns made from several fibers, and filament yarns made from tows by direct twisting. may be threads. In general, it can be classified according to raw material, yarn diameter, spinning method, spinning system, yarn structure and assembly. In this article, we will talk about threads and their types, their importance in the field of production. Today, technologies are developing day by day, and the industrial sector has a small place among them. With the development of technologies, it is also very important to use yarns in the manufacturing sector and distinguish them by type.*

Key words: *Thread, fibers, zhongte, yarns, embroidery threads longitudinal yarns, fabrics.*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7729761>

INTRODUCTION: Thread - fibers (spun or unspun textile and sewing material made of cotton, silk, wool, linen; knitted and crocheted products. Gauzes, knitting, sewing clothes, etc. evaluation in many ways. Options for getting thread. Fiber type. Depending on the type of yarn, it is divided into natural, artificial, mineral.) is cooked a lot, and the worsted yarn is cooked less, and the yarn for knitting is cooked even less. Silk yarn spun from cocoon fibers; complex yarns from viscose, acetate, kapron, etc. problematic fibers.

MATERIALS AND DISCUSSION:

According to thread materials

1. Pure spinning: Pure spinning is made from fibrous materials such as cotton yarn, wool yarn, hemp yarn and silk yarn. This type of yarn is suitable for the production of clean textiles.
2. Blended yarn: Blended yarns are made of two or more fibers, such as polyester and cotton blended yarns, wool and viscose blended yarns, etc. These yarns are used in fabrics that emphasize the advantages of both fibers.

By thread size

1. Coarse text thread: Coarse text thread refers to threads of 32 tex and above (18 English thread and below). This type of thread is suitable for thick fabrics such as tweed and plain cloth.
2. ZHONGTE thread: ZHONGTE thread refers to 21 ~ 32 tex (19 ~ 28 English thread). This type of thread is suitable for medium and thick fabrics, such as plain cloth, gabardine, khaki, etc.
3. Fine text thread: fine text thread means 11 ~ 20 tex (29 ~ 54 English thread). This type of thread is suitable for delicate fabrics, such as delicate fabric, poplin, etc.

4. Fine yarns: Fine yarns refer to yarns of 10 tex or less (58 count or more). This type of thread is suitable for high-quality delicate fabrics, such as shirts, sweaters wrapped in shirts, etc.

Through the spinning system

1. Bow yarn: worsted yarn, also called worsted yarn, produced by carding process, including worsted cotton and worsted yarn. The fiber in the yarn has a high parallel plane, is uniformly dry and smooth, but the price is high and the support of the yarn is high. Combed yarn is mainly used for high-quality fabric and knitting raw materials, such as spinning, Huada, flower, wool, etc.

2. Carriage: worsted yarn, also known as coarse carded or plain carded cotton yarn, refers to yarn that is carded according to the common spinning system and not spun in the carding process. Rope yarn has more short fiber, poor fiber parallel plane, loose structure, more wool, low thread count and low quality. This type of yarn is mainly used for general fabric and knitting raw materials, such as wool fabric, medium and special cotton fabric, etc.

3. Waste spinning: Waste spinning refers to threads made from textile scraps (waste cotton) or mixed with low-quality raw materials. The quality of the thread is low, soft, uneven, contains various things, the color is bad, it is usually used to weave coarse cotton blankets, thick flannel and packaging fabrics and other low-quality fabrics.

On the use of threads

1. Weaving yarn: the yarn used for machinery refers to the yarn used to process woven fabrics, which can be divided into warp yarn and weft yarn. Textile yarns are used as longitudinal yarns with large twist, high strength and good wear resistance; Textile yarn is used as the cross yarn of fabric, it has the characteristics of small twist, low strength and softness.

2. Knitting yarn: Knitting yarn is a yarn used for knitting fabric. The requirements for thread quality are high, the twist is small and the strength is average.

3. other threads: includes sewing threads, embroidery threads, knitting threads, various threads, etc. According to different purposes, the requirements for these threads are different.

CONCLUSION: In the boxes of the house, useful little things are stored, perhaps among them there is a bag with unnamed or numbered skeins of threads of different colors. Stocks of these handicrafts were carefully handed down through inheritance or perhaps left over from long school days. Today, the frugal collection of scarce yarns has been replaced by variety and availability. Russian and foreign manufacturers attract with their palette of color cards, which can be viewed online and ordered with home delivery. In conclusion, choosing a thread and being able to unravel it is a great art.

REFERENCES:

1. Gibson P, Kendrick C, Rivin D, Sicutanza L. An Automated Water Vapor Diffusion Test Method for Fabrics, Laminates, and Films. *Journal of Industrial Textile* 1995; 24, 4.
2. Kissa E. Wetting and Wicking. *Textile Research Journal* 1996; 66, 10.
3. Fan J, Wang H W K. Review of Heat and Water Vapor Transfer Through Multilayer Fabrics. *Textile Research Journal* 2008; 86, 3